
THE USE OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS IN TEACHING THE DISCIPLINE THE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Annotation

The article discusses the use of mobile applications in teaching students the discipline of using information technology in professional activities using modern information technologies. The main attention is paid to the qualitative use of information and communication technologies in the course of the lesson.

Keywords

educational process, information communication, Internet information, mobile operating systems, mobile applications.

The main purpose of the introduction and use of information technologies in education is to create new opportunities for all participants in the educational process, that is, recipients and givers of education.

The widespread introduction of information technologies into the educational process gives:

reduction of time spent on the search for educational and scientific information by students and teachers;

acceleration of changes in the content of e-learning literature depending on the requirements of the period;

allocation of additional time for students to study independently.

The use of mobile applications in teaching young students the science of using information technologies in professional activities using modern information technologies is one of the current topics of today. Today, mobile devices have become of great importance in people's lives. Thus, the need for mobile applications is growing by itself. Mobile apps-smartphones and tablets software developed for mobile devices such as. They turn mobile devices into functional and fun miniature forces. It will be pre-installed with certain cellular applications from some device manufacturers or cellular service providers they are associated with. Many online facilities have mobile websites and mobile apps. Overall, the

difference lies in one goal: the app is generally smaller in size than a mobile website, offers more interactivity and offers more accurate information, easy to use and intuitive on a mobile device. A mobile application developer creates a special application for the operating system on which he works. For example, mobile apps for iPad work on Apple iOS, but not on Google Android. The Apple app doesn't work on an Android phone, and vice versa. Most often, developers create versions of each of them. For example, a mobile app in the Apple Store may also have an android version on Google Play.

Using modern technologies for creating mobile applications using the capabilities of computers in the educational process, the creation of electronic educational materials, visual aids, training mobile applications designed for non-traditional lessons that allow students to gain knowledge and determine their level of knowledge in a timely manner, the creation of educational control programs and their implementation in the educational process is one of the most important tasks of today.

Currently, there are many mobile applications that help students gain knowledge and determine their level of knowledge in a timely manner. Examples include Phomath, Duolingo: language Lesson, Moddle, Hemis, Macrat Academy.

Duolingo is an educational app that is the most popular app in the world. English language skills through practice

Improvement-designed for reading, talking, writing and listening. While playing the game, there are quests to answer questions, increase your vocabulary and improve grammar.

You can use this mobile app for the following purposes:

- Fopydal of courses even offline;
- Receive instant notifications about messages and other events;
- Quickly find and communicate with other course participants;
- Download images, audio, video and other files from a mobile device;
- View course grades;
- and so on.
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- View course grades;
- and so on.

This mobile application is designed for teaching foreign languages. With the Ibrat Academy mobile app, you can learn the necessary languages anywhere online.

The following applications are used to teach students and determine their level of knowledge in a timely manner. In addition, there are software tools with interactive methods of using information technology in professional activities for the purpose of exciting coursework for future teachers. Kahoot as one of such software tools! an example application can be given. Kahoot! It is a free tool that allows education professionals the opportunity to teach in a fun and engaging way, making it a very rewarding interactive experience. Such a program can be used on computers or mobile devices. The best thing about this tool is that it perfectly combines learning with entertainment, which is important because students learn with pleasure and without boredom. Speaking about how Kahoot works, it should be noted that there are two different stages.

At the first stage, the specialist must register in order to be able to use the program. This is a quick and easy step where you have to choose one of four possible profiles: teacher, student, personal and professional use.

The second stage is nothing more than the application of such a tool in practice. There is an option that allows you to use the tool without registration. A person is known as a guest and can perform various little things or kahoots.

The first is to open the program on your computer and go to a web page. The teacher will be responsible for setting the various rules and regulations of this game. The key is to determine whether it will be a round or a team competition. After setting up the game type, the tool will generate a PIN code. Players can then join the game from another computer or mobile device.

After opening the app, you will need to enter a PIN code to participate in the game. The moderator is responsible for determining the start time of the game. When you press the Start button, a question and four possible answers are displayed on the screen. Participants answer and get points if they do it correctly. The winner is the participant who gives the most correct answers.

In short, the Kahoot tool is perfect for both teachers and students, as it allows you to learn in a fun and engaging way. New technologies have made an app like Kahoot a part of everyday learning and learning in many parts of the world.

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